

THE ROLE OF STANDARDIZATION IN MODERN PRODUCTION

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In today's world, the importance of standards is constantly growing. The main reason for this is the changes in the economy and social life associated with the globalization of the world market, the erasure of boundaries in the way of the movement of capital, goods, ideas and information. Scientific and technological progress, the rapid development of information technologies and their active implementation - all this also contributed to the intensification of the process of development and implementation of international standards in all areas of human activity, including in document management.

The International Organization for Standardization (ISO) is a worldwide association of national standardization bodies (ISO member organizations). The preparation of International Standards is usually carried out in the relevant ISO technical committees. Each ISO member organization has the right to be represented on those technical committees, the topics of which correspond to its interests. International organizations, both governmental and non-governmental, also take part in this work.

Due to the successful use of ISO quality standards, as well as in connection with the global trend of tightening regulatory requirements to the conduct of financial and economic activities, there is a growing need throughout the world to develop a unified approach to solving the most common issues that are important for any of the existing office systems.

ISO has defined its objectives for the end of the century, and at the beginning of the new millennium, highlighting the most relevant strategic areas of work:

- establishing closer links between the organization's activities and the market, which should primarily be reflected in the choice of priority developments;
- reduction of general and time costs as a result of increasing the efficiency of the administrative apparatus, better use of human resources, optimization of the work process, development of information technologies and telecommunications;
- providing effective assistance to the World Trade Organization through the implementation of a program focused on the gradual processing of technical conditions for the supply of goods into ISO standards;
- stimulating "self-supporting" elements of the above program: encouraging the creation of new standards for industry, developing relations with the WTO on the terms of providing the necessary technical assistance. In particular, it is intended to contribute in every possible way to the inclusion of requirements for products supplied by states in international ISO standards, which should have a positive impact on the recognition of conformity assessment;
- concern for improving the quality of national standardization activities in developing countries, where the main attention is paid to leveling the levels of standardization.

Thanks to the successful use of ISO quality standards, as well as in connection with the global trend of tightening legal and regulatory requirements for conducting financial and economic activities, there is a growing need throughout the world to develop a unified approach to solving the most common issues that are important for any of the existing office work systems.

Organizations are required to develop rules for working with documents, including issues of protection, search, determination of retention periods and controlled destruction of documents with expired retention periods. To comply with the requirements of the standard, it is necessary to prepare a large number of internal regulatory documents and regularly make changes and improvements to them.